

Patterns of Expression of Human Papilloma Virus Gene Products In Cases of Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma: Findings From a University Teaching Hospital in Northern Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) is a well-recognized oncogenic virus in several epithelial malignancies of the head and neck; however, its role in the aetio-pathogenesis of Nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) remains controversial and appears to vary by geographic region and histologic subtype. Data on HPV involvement in NPC are limited in Nigeria. This study was therefore undertaken to determine the presence of HPV DNA in NPC tissues from patients seen at Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital (ABUTH), Zaria, Nigeria. A retrospective analysis of 44 histologically confirmed NPC cases diagnosed between 1992 and 2013 was carried out. Formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded (FFPE) tissue blocks were retrieved and DNA was extracted using a commercial FFPE DNA extraction kit. DNA quality was assessed by Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) amplification of the human β -globin gene, while HPV DNA detection was performed using GP5+/GP6+ consensus primers targeting the L1 region of the HPV genome, with appropriate positive and negative controls included. All samples showed adequate DNA quality with successful β -globin amplification; however, none of the 44 NPC cases demonstrated detectable HPV DNA by PCR. These findings suggest that HPV may not play a significant role in the pathogenesis of NPC in this environment and support the predominance of non-HPV-related aetiological factors, such as Epstein-Barr virus, in NPC within this population. Further studies using larger sample sizes and complementary detection methods are recommended.

Keywords: HPV, Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma, PCR

INTRODUCTION

Human Papilloma Virus (HPV) is a small, non-enveloped, epitheliotropic, double-stranded DNA virus that infects mucosal and cutaneous epithelia and induces cellular proliferation. Over 100 types have been identified and designated “high-risk” or “low-risk” depending on their potential for carcinogenicity, notably in the genital tract and the head and neck regions.¹ Recognized high-risk types include HPV types-16, 18, 31, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 56, 58, 59, 68, 73, and 82; and low-risk types include

HPV types- 6, 11, 40, 42, 43, 44, 54, 61, 72, 81, and 89.^{1,2}

All HPV genomes contain approximately eight open-reading frames (ORFs) divided into the early region encoding proteins E1–E7 (necessary for viral replication); the late region encoding the structural proteins L1 and L2 (required for virion assembly); and the largely non-coding long control region (LCR), necessary for the replication and transcription of viral DNA.³ The early proteins E5, E6 and E7 have been identified as key proteins in the

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mechanisms of HPV carcinogenesis. The best known property of the E6 proteins of high-risk HPVs is the inability to bind and degrade the tumour-suppressor protein p53 through the recruitment of the protein ligase, E6-associated protein (E6-AP) resulting in the inhibition of the transcriptional activity of p53 and the abrogation of p53-induced apoptosis.³ In addition, E6 induces the expression and activity of telomerase responsible for cell immortalization⁴ E7 protein also induces apoptosis through the destabilization of p105Rb, a negative regulator of the cell cycle. Another important aspect of E7 biology is its ability to destabilize centrosomes, which cause mitotic defects and genome instability^{3,5} E5 protein enhances the immortalization potential of E6 and E7 while also directly inhibiting apoptosis that is induced by ultraviolet (UV) light, Fas-ligand and tumour necrosis factor related apoptosis-inducing ligand.⁶

Well recognized high-risk HPV types, including HPV16, 18 and 31, have been linked to Head and Neck Squamous Cell Carcinoma (HNSCC)⁷. Given this known oncogenic role of HPV in epithelial cancers of head & neck, there has been growing interest in its role in the aetio-pathogenesis of Nasopharyngeal Carcinoma (NPC). Recently, several studies have examined HPV DNA, expression of E6/E7 and expression of p16 (a surrogate marker for HPV oncogenic activity). A systematic review and meta-analysis by Zhao et al found an overall global prevalence of HPV-positive NPC of about 18% among 6,314 NPC patients from 46 studies. These showed regional variation, with higher incidence in the non-endemic North America, and lower incidence in the endemic region of Asia.⁸ Another meta-analysis on viral markers in NPC reported HPV DNA prevalence of 34.4% in WHO type I NPC, versus 18.4% in WHO types II/III.⁹ Although HPV DNA is detectable in a subset of NPCs, consistent and strong evidence of active viral gene product expression (E6/E7 transcripts or proteins) is relatively scarce in NPC compared to that seen in cervical cancer or oropharyngeal carcinoma, and prevalence varies by region, histologic subtype and detection methods.

A more consistent aetiological relationship is seen between NPC and Epstein-Barr Virus (EBV)

especially the non-keratinising carcinoma (NKC) histologic subtype in endemic areas (Southern China, Southeast Asia).^{10,11} Curiously, HPV appears to modulate EBV biology in NPC as patients with HPV-EBV co-infection seem to be younger and have higher rates of radiation and chemotherapy responses as well as long-term survival with excellent prognosis.^{9,12} The prevailing opinion is increasingly that such patients should be referred to individual therapeutic regimens that are adapted to their HPV-status, which differs from therapeutic strategies for HPV-negative patients. These HPV-positive NPC subsets have been observed to occur more frequently in Caucasians of European ancestry, but they are still poorly understood.^{12,13} Furthermore, little is known about the prevalence of oncogenic HPV in NPC and its clinical significance in our environment. We were therefore particularly interested in examining HPV expression in NPC tissues due to its therapeutic and prognostic relevance and because none of the previous Nigerian studies on HPV had examined this.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study included 44 cases of histologically diagnosed NPC seen at the Department of Pathology, ABUTH Shika-Zaria from January 1, 1992 to December 31, 2013. Formalin-fixed, paraffin-embedded tissues (FFPE) of all previously diagnosed NPCs within the study period were retrieved and examined with the exclusion of missing, badly damaged, or FFPE with insufficient tissue.

Deparaffinization: About 5-8 freshly cut sections were made from the PETB, each with a thickness of up to 10 µm and a surface area of up to 250 mm². The tumoural tissues were retrieved by dewaxing the thin tissue sections in 1mL of xylene and vortexed for 10 seconds. Tubes were then centrifuged at 14,000 rpm for 2 minutes and the supernatant (xylene) was removed carefully by pipetting. To the pellets at the bottom of the tube, 1ml of 96% ethanol was added and vortexed vigorously for 10 seconds before centrifugation at 14,000rpm for 2 minutes. The supernatant (ethanol) was removed by pipetting and the tubes were opened and incubated at room temperature until the ethanol evaporated.

DNA Extraction: EBV DNA was extracted by means of an enzymatic digestion. Genomic DNA extraction was carried out using *QIAamp*® DNA FFPE Tissue kit and performed precisely according to the manufacturer's instruction except for *Proteinase K* digestion which was allowed to stay overnight for complete digestion of the tissues. Pellets were re-suspended in 180 µL ATL buffer and 20 µL of proteinase K was added and allowed to digest overnight at 56°C. After overnight incubation, the tubes were allowed to cool then incubated at 96°C for 1hr. Tubes were cooled again and 400 µL of Buffer AL-alcohol mixture (1:1) was added and vortexed vigorously. The entire mixture was carefully transferred to the *QIAamp MinElute* column (in a 2 ml collection tube) and centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 1 minute. Changing the collection tubes each time, AW1 and AW2 solutions were used to wash, by centrifuging for 1 minute at 8000 rpm. The spin column was dried to remove all traces of alcohol by centrifuging the spin columns at 14,000 rpm for 3 minutes. To the dried spin column, 100 µL of TE buffer was added directly to the spin column and allowed to equilibrate for 2 minutes before centrifugation at 8000 rpm for 1 minute. The eluted DNA was stored at -20°C.

DNA quantification: DNA was quantified using NanoDrop 2000C spectrophotometer (Thermo Scientific, USA). Concentration was determined based on absorbance at 260nm. Purity was estimated as ratio of absorbance at 260nm to Absorbance at 280nm (A260:A280).

Polymerase Chain reaction (PCR): PCR for beta Hemoglobin: PCR was run for human Hb-beta subunit to ascertain the quality of the extracted DNA, the viability of the tissue for PCR detection of HPV and as a control gene for human tissues. A primer which targets a 122 bp sequence of the Hb beta subunit was used, both forward (5'cttctgacacaactgtgttctactagc 3') and reverse (5'tcaccacaacttcatccacgttcacc 3') primers were obtained from *Inqaba Biotech West Africa*. PCR was carried out in a 25 µL reaction using One Taq Quick-load Master Mix (New England Biolab). And amplification was carried out using *Mastercycler Nexus* (Eppendorf, Germany).

Gel Electrophoresis: To confirm amplification of the 120 bp *Hb beta* sub-unit, agarose gel electrophoresis was carried out on 1.2% agarose in TAE buffer according to method suggested by Green and Sambrook.¹⁴ Electrophoresis was carried out at 90V for 30min and viewed under UV trans-illuminator. A 100 kb size ladder (*Promega*) was used as the standard size DNA marker and staining was done with Ethidium Bromide.

PCR for HPV using GP5+/GP6+ primers: Only Samples that show positive amplification of the Hb beta sub-unit were selected for the HPV PCR. PCR was carried out with the primer GP5+/GP6+ and using the protocol suggested by Evans *et al.*, with the following sequence; GP5+ [5'-TTTGTACTGTGGTAGATACTAC-3'] and GP6+ [5'-GAAAAATAAACTGTAAATCATATTC-3']. The primer targets the L1 region of the HPV genome and amplifies HPV of all types.¹⁵⁻¹⁷ PCR was carried out in a 25 µL reaction using One Taq Quick-load Master Mix (New England Biolab). PCR reactions contain 1.25 U Taq polymerase in standard buffer containing 1.8mM MgCl₂, 22 mM NH₄Cl, 22 mM KCl, 0.2 µM each of forward and reverse primers and 200 µM dNTPs. To each reaction, 2 µL of extracted DNA of template DNA was added.

For negative controls a mixture of all the reagents were used in the PCR mixture preparation with the addition of 1µl of sterile distilled water instead of DNA. For the positive control a preformed HPV from tissue culture was used. The data obtained were statistically analyzed using the Microsoft Excel and presented as simple frequencies in tables and charts.

Ethical approval was obtained from the Ethics and Research Committee of Ahmadu Bello University Teaching Hospital Zaria (ABUTH/HREC/K21/2014).

RESULTS

Real-time PCR detection of HPV done for 44 cases showed no positivity.

Figure 1: Gel electrophoresis image of PCR detection for HPV. Wells not showing any band are negative. No amplification was observed in the samples. Positive control HPV showed positive band of 155bp Size.

DISCUSSION

The real-time PCR gene detection for HPV done for 44 cases showed no positivity. Markedly contrasting with a previous study of the same population which reported 37.2% positivity for EBV using a similar real-time PCR method.¹¹ HPV detection in NPC has been carried out by various approaches including consensus PCR (often targeting L1 region with primers such as GP5⁺/GP6⁺ or MY09/MY11), type-specific PCR, in-situ hybridisation (ISH) of HPV DNA, immunohistochemistry for surrogate markers (p16), and more recently E6/E7 mRNA assays. These studies show wide variability in the expression of HPV in NPC perhaps due to the differences in the sensitivity of viral detection methods used and geographical variations.

Identical to the finding in our study, a study in Japan among 43 NPC patients similarly found that no cases were HPV-positive when tested for HPV DNA using ISH.¹⁸ They also found that 14% were EBV-negative with keratinization squamous cell carcinoma (KSCC) and the rest were EBV-positive (86%). A more recent study in the same country among 26 NPC patients (2015-2022) showed 4% prevalence of HPV and 73% prevalence of EBV.¹⁹ These findings would suggest that HPV plays a very limited role for HPV in the development of NPC in non-endemic regions.

However, a slightly higher prevalence is seen in some studies among non-endemic populations. In one study in the UK of 67 NPC cases, HPV DNA was sought by ISH, PCR (GP5⁺/GP6⁺) and p16 IHC and found that 16.4% were HPV DNA positive and 70.1% were EBV-positive.²⁰ In Accra-Ghana, out of 72 FFPE NPC biopsies, HPV DNA was present in

19.2% of the cases and EBV DNA was present in 25% of the cases.²¹ A much higher prevalence is reported from a study in Morocco where 70 NPC biopsies tested for HPV DNA using consensus primers showed about 34% positivity.²²

Generally, viral detection by PCR has been found to be affected by several factors including the type and duration of fixation, prolonged archiving of PETB, and the RNA/DNA extraction methods.²³⁻²⁵ The type of fixative used routinely for specimens in our laboratory is 10% neutral formal saline and specimens are kept for a duration of 24-48 hours, long enough for adequate fixation. Formalin-fixed archival samples were thought to be poor materials for molecular biological applications, however Masuda et al analyzed the modification of formalin fixation and found that de-modification (by proteinase K and temperature elevation) enabled extraction of RNA from fixed samples to the same amount as from fresh samples or at least removed more than half of the modification.²⁵

The oldest specimen in our study was archived for a period of about 21 years at the time of the study. In a comprehensive study using a large number of decades-old samples of over 20 years, similar to ours, Iwamoto et al concluded that the age of the test samples was not as great a problem as was the source of procurement, thus extracted DNA can be used for all types of assays that require PCR amplification, such as restriction fragment length polymorphism, single-strand conformation polymorphism, and direct sequencing. They demonstrated the feasibility of using decades-old archival tissues for use in large-scale molecular studies.²⁶ Considering the adequate fixation of tissues in our study and the proven

feasibility of PCR in archived FFPE tissues, DNA degradation due to poor sample quality is an improbable explanation for the lack of HPV expression in NPC in this study but rather due to other biological and technical reasons.

Firstly, studies have shown that the L1 gene consensus primers (GP5⁺/GP6⁺), used in this study, may be undetected at low viral loads even with PCR amplification.²⁷ The viral load in non-cervical sites, including the nasopharynx, have also been shown to be much lower or distribution more heterogeneously, so consensus L1 primers may be sub-optimal.²⁸ Similarly, sampling bias due to tumour heterogeneity and contamination with non-tumour tissue as well as co-infection with EBV may complicate HPV detection resulting in widely varied prevalence coupled with differing detection methods.⁸

In addition, a major event in high-risk HPV-related carcinogenesis is integration of the viral genome into the host genome which involves the disruption of the E1/E2 genes (that regulate E6/E7) and may also truncate or delete other regions including the late genes L1/L2.^{29,30} A recent study found that L1 expression in oesophageal and other cancers declines with advancement of the disease, associated with progressive viral integration and a simultaneous upregulation of p16.³¹ HPV testing that primarily targets L1, as this study does, may be less reliable than that targeting E6/E7 oncogenes, as L1 expression can be lost while E6/E7 expression is almost always present.^{27,29,30} Even without deletion, the late genes (including L1) may be silenced epigenetically (via methylation of viral DNA, histone modifications) or by host regulatory mechanisms once integration occurs and the virus moves from a replicative to transforming mode. The disruption of E2, changes in upstream regulatory region (URR) methylation, and reduced expression of viral late transcripts are observed.³² Furthermore, EBV is the dominant etiologic virus in the aetio-pathogenesis of NPCs, therefore, HPV may play a secondary or incidental role and may be present in a latent or integrated form which may reduce expression and explain the lack of L1 gene expression and detection.

Finally, a comparative study of HPV18 in NPC and

cervical cancer noted that the expression levels of E6/E7 differed between the two sites (higher E6 in cervical, higher E7 in NPC). It also noted variation in the L1 region sequences and LCR region in NPC compared with cervical cancer, suggesting adaptation of virus at different sites³³. These site-specific differences in viral pathogenesis in NPC may further suggest a lower L1 expression and detection.

CONCLUSION

The observed lack of expression of HPV in NPC in this study is likely multifactorial reflecting a combination of technical and biological realities. For studies in NPC, it is advisable to adopt a more comprehensive HPV testing strategy including E6/E7 detection, integration assessment, and good quality samples, to avoid underestimating HPV's potential role. In NPC research, given the dominance of EBV, it may be helpful to test for both viruses and evaluate viral load, integration status, and surrogate markers (p16, E6/E7) rather than relying solely on one method.

Recommendation

The interpretation of negative PCR results should be done cautiously, as they may reflect technical limitation or viral genome disruption rather than a true absence of HPV.

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